

THE METAPHOR OF “USONG-AFERE” AND THE NIGERIAN MASSES: A CRITIQUE OF NIGERIA’S POLITICAL EXPERIENCE

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*Democracy,
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Abstract: *This essay presents a critical analysis of the dismal relationship between some Nigerian politicians and the electorates described as the fate of usong-afere in the pot of white soup. Nigerian electorates are often used hypothetically as means to achieve political ends during the election seasons only to be forgotten and abandoned during governance. This scenario has raised much concern among the populace. The questions often asked are why do politicians abandon the electorates during governance? Why do they often fail to fulfil their campaign promises? Is this kind of attitude normal? The aim of this paper is to expose the behavior of some politicians as anomaly for, the 1999 constitution of Nigeria spells out welfare of Nigerians and protection of lives and property as the foremost responsibility of government and the 1945 act of the United Nations obliges political officer to champion protection of fundamental human rights, maintenance of law and enforcement of fairness and justice among other values and principles of democracy which is government of the people by the people. These principles seem to be grossly lacking in Nigeria. Critical analysis of concepts is the method used in this discourse. This work exposing the ills of some members of the political class will be educating Nigerians and people of other climes on the dismal experience of democracy. It can also offer some benefits to the members of the political class who may be ignorant of their selfish practices in the pretext of ‘nascent’ democratic governance.*

1. Introduction

Some people and items are often treated based on their intrinsic value whereas others, based on the utility derived from them. In most cases,

items and people that are valued based on their extrinsic worth do not imply that they are bereft

of intrinsic values. It is just that such people or things are needed hypothetically at that moment. When things are used to achieve a

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certain end, there may be little and no moral cum ethical questions but not humans. However, when people are used to achieving an end, there could arise a plethora of moral cum ethical questions. Using a person or people to achieve an end implies a reduction from personhood to a mere thing or object. The metaphor of *usong-afere* is a clear example of how a thing is used to achieve an end after which it is discarded. The fate of *usong-afere* in the pot of soup is clearly analogous to how most Nigeria politicians relate with the electorates.

Usong-afere is a lump of pounded yam purposely added and vital to a pot of white soup meant for eating pounded yam. This dish is special in all the tribes in Akwa Ibom and Cross River States of Nigeria. *Usong-afere* serves the function of thickening soup and thus, making the soup more delicious and more appetizing. *Usong-afere* is a *conditio sine qua non* in a typical pot of white soup made by people from the above-mentioned cultures. However, *usong-afere* suffers a terrible fate: After thickening the soup, making it more delicious and more appetizing, it is thrown out into the dustbin. It is not eaten, it is no longer needed, because it has accomplished its purpose. Most Nigerian politicians treat the electorates in the same way as *usong-afere* in the pot of soup.

Political enlightenment is deepened and more penetrating even in the interiors. The electorates are more aware of their power (in the Private voter Card PVC). The PVC is the power of the electorates during election seasons. The usual

Nigeria's political campaigns take aspirants together with their supporters to different places, even the abandoned interiors. To the electorate, they make lofty campaign promises such as creating job opportunities, road construction, establishment of factories and industries, establishment of schools and healthcare facilities among others. At the time of the promise, they often used meagre amounts of money together with food stuff (often, rice) to buy off the promises made to the people. A commentator in one of Nigeria's national Newspaper expressed the frustration of Nigerians "Our politicians are at it again. They are in their element, doing what they know how to do best—politicking without any thought for good governance. It is about capturing power, not proving their worth or earning the trust of the electorate" (Adetayo, Punch Newspaper). The frustration explained here is made on behalf of all Nigerians, for if every Nigerian is to publish his frustrations on the political leaders, deepest outcries will abound. The deception by politicians is intentional and the economic hardship seems like a tool with which they control the electorate thereby offering them peanuts. These peanuts in Nigeria's contemporary political lexicon are tagged "palliatives". In most cases, these so-called palliatives at campaign arenas are aimed at vote buying in disguise, but electorates have the civic responsibility of resisting vote buying by rejecting any offer. However, pangs of hunger in the stomach will not let them resist yielding to

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the evil they already know. Some of the politicians know fully well that they are into business and so, whatever they spend during electioneering must be recovered if they are elected to office.

This essay exposes the anomaly in democratic governance in Nigeria. It defends that Nigerian electorates are treated like *usong-afere*, a treatment that demeans the dignity of their human person. The reason for this experience is multi-dimensional. Included are the political culture of Nigeria, socioeconomic condition among others. This essay sympathizes with the electorates despite their culpability by taking “palliatives” from politicians who have weaponized poverty to their advantage. This work is presented in six sections: Section one presents the general introduction to the work. Section two introduces the work, brings to the fore an analysis of *usong-afere* and its implications for Nigerian electorates. Section three presents an exposition of the prevalent attitude of politicians. Section four describes the challenging daily life of Nigerian masses. Section five juxtaposes the fate of *usong-afere* and the Nigerian politicians describing it as an anomaly needing responsibility espoused by Emmanuel Levinas’ ethics. Section six concludes that welfare of the electorates is primordial in Nigeria’s constitution as well as United Nations acta and must be upheld. Similarly, a political officer’s oath of office obligates them to care for the electorates and as such, *usong-afere*

treatment is anomaly normalized in Nigeria’s democratic experience.

2. Analysis of the Metaphor of “Usong-afere”

Pounded yam is a special dish for people from some cultures especially in the southern region of Nigeria. This kind of dish has a special or customized soup called *afia-afere* which makes a fantastic combination for consuming it. *Usong-edia*, pounded yam is a special dish especially in Annang land. Notedly, it is one of the best Christmas dishes as well as one presented to one’s special guests. Nigeria’s history agrees that pounded yam dish is a typical Nigeria’s Christmas food among others (Nigeria’s 50th Independence, p.183). Pounded yam must be complemented with its special soup, *afia-afere* of which *usong-afere* is an indispensable ingredient for making the soup. *Usong-afere* is a lump of pounded yam purposely added to a pot of white soup meant to be used to eat pounded yam in almost all tribes in Akwa Ibom and Cross River States of Nigeria. Nigeria as a country is blessed with diversity of people and variety of culture and traditions which also immensely informs her rich food varieties. Nigeria’s food heritage is rooted in antiquity related with life and religion (Nigeria’s 50th Independence, p. 182). *Usong-afere*, a lump of yam in soup serves the function of thickening the soup and thus making the soup more delicious and more appetizing. *Usong-afere* is a *conditio sine qua non* in a typical pot

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of white soup made by people from the above cultures and beyond. However, *usong-afere* suffers a terrible fate: after thickening the soup, making it more delicious and more appetizing, it is thrown out into the dustbin. It is not eaten; it is no longer needed because it has fulfilled its purpose.

Usong-afere, together with other ingredients, make a delicious pot of soup which everyone treats themselves to. Although *Usong-afere* is the most important ingredient in the dish but often jettisoned while serving the soup, other less important ingredients are consumed along with the *Usong-edia* and the *afere*. The implication of this is that the desired part of the *usong-afere* has been extracted into the soup during the process of the soup making when it was being cooked. The extracted part of the *usong-afere* is the “characteristic excellence”, the essence of the *usong-afere* whereas the part discarded is useless.

Afia afere as the people of antiquity often prepared would lose its essence without the use of *usong-afere*. There are, however, some people who “adulterate” *afia afere* – this means cooking it without the use of *usong-afere*. This kind of *afia afere* is deficient of the traditional ingredient and hence, the taste of the people of Annang of antiquity. Hence, it is not what it is meant to be. It is *afia afere unana usong-afere* (white soup without *usong-afere*)! It is the *usong-afere* that is the substratum of the *afia afere* customized for pounded yam as originally prepared by the ancient Annang people.

From the above analysis, the essence and the importance of *usong afere* cannot be rightly neglected in original pot of *afia afere*. For negligence of it amounts to losing its essence. *Usong-afere*, therefore, having this irreplaceable importance in *afia-afere* is noteworthy and must be treated commensurately for the impact it offers. However, does the irreplaceable impact of *usong-afere* in the pot of *afia afere* make any change in the ill-fate of the *usong-afere*? The fate, ill treatment, the dishonorable end of the proverbial *usong-afere* – a once important, irreplaceable, indispensable recipe of *afia afere* is forgotten. It is not eaten but thrown away after it has fulfilled its role in the soup. It was not needed for what it is, but for what it could offer. It was not needed for its intrinsic worth but derived value. It has not a categorical use but only a hypothetical use and so *usong-afere* must be jettisoned when the food is done as some people do. Three possible ways of discarding it from the pot of soup are: firstly, it is thrown out once the cook notices that the pot of soup is completely cooked. Secondly, it is thrown out of the pot when serving the soup as some do. Thirdly, it is abandoned in the pot of soup only to be thrown away after completely eating the meal and then the pot and other dishes are ready to be washed.

The fate of *usong-afere* is one, absolute and conclusive, namely, being jettisoned after fulfilling its role in the pot of soup. This conclusion is one and true regardless of method

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and time of its jettisoning. *Usong-afere* having fulfilled its function in the pot of *afia afere* is thrown out into *iton* - a place in the household where waste materials are heaped. *Usong-afere* has no future in the pot of *afia afere*. Despite its irreplaceable role in the soup, it has no secure future. Fresh ones can always be used only when needed. It does not need to be preserved for another time, nor does it need to be accorded some respect for its importance because it can always be grabbed from the mortar while pounding it. Such is the fate of Nigerian masses in the current so-called Nigeria's democratic experience. Such is the attitude of most Nigerian politicians towards the electorates in Nigeria's experience of democracy. To fully grasp the fate of Nigeria's masses vis-à-vis the proverbial *usong-afere*, the exposition of the attitude of Nigeria's politicians toward the masses is pivotal.

3) Attitudinal exposition of Nigerian politicians

Attitude refers to an established way of thinking, feeling and acting toward another person or something. It concerns the mental and emotional inclination of a person, object, or situation. The feeling may be described positive when it is favorable to the person and negative if it is detrimental to the person's wellbeing and welfare. A person's attitude includes one's tendency and orientation, disposition to feel, talk and act toward another person or other people. Furthermore, by "attitudinal disposition" of Nigerian politicians, this article

refers to most politicians' ingrained, habitual, or characteristic manner of thinking, feeling, behaving and acting toward the masses of the Nigerian society and their life specific situations. It envelops the underlying mental state or tendency that dictates how the majority of politicians relate with and treat the people, including their constituents, after they are voted into political offices. The said treatment is, nevertheless, negative because it undermines human dignity, wellbeing and welfare. The treatment is antithetical to the promises they make during campaigns.

Having consistently studied this consistent dismal and infra dig attitude, one is compelled to juxtapose it to some intellectual interrogations. Since the etymological definition of philosophy wants us to understand it as love of wisdom, and since philosophy is said to be the mother of all disciplines, philosophical principles and ideas are quite apt for this scrutiny. A philosopher once said that human beings in their actions should choose maxims that can be universalized – that which if everyone acted in a similar way, it would be acceptable. Succinctly, Immanuel Kant in his formulation of the categorical imperative distinguished it from the hypothetical imperative. In his original formulation, he states: "Act only according to that maxim whereby you can at the same time will that it should become a universal law" (1948, p. 88). The reasoning behind this formulation is that Kant understands a maxim as a personal rule for action. This is an ideal in Kant's

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reasoning. He advocates that whatever anyone adopts as a maxim, such a person should will that the maxim be universalized by everyone, and always. Kant believes that his formulation will avoid any sort of logical contradiction while gaining broad spectrum alignment and acceptability, hence, a universal rule. In this formulation Kant comes against implicating the notions of categorical and hypothetical imperatives.

Hypothetical imperatives are self-driven commands which an individual appeals to and employs to attend certain self-motivated goals and advantages. It is typically selfish and has nothing to offer the other. Hypothetical imperatives originate from selfish motivations, driven by personal inclination, happiness, self-advantage and fulfilment. Using the unchangeable variable of this paper, *usong-afere*, which is hypothetically used by a cook as a vital and irreplaceable recipe in her dish. She does not use it because she wants the *usong-afere* for itself but for what it can offer. Following this analysis, most Nigerian politicians betray themselves by their attitude which are selfish, self-seeking vying solely for their advantage and perpetuity. Everything they say and do during campaigns is superficial and meant to falsely entice the masses for the sake of their selfish goals. In contemporary Nigerian slang, they are for the optics! The relationship between the politicians and the masses may be described as erotic, because they use the people to attain their pleasure and happiness. They have no sympathy,

no respect, and care not about the welfare of the people. Indeed, their treatment of the people has been described as “toilet roll treatment” (Agomuo, 2025). Toilet roll is a household item needed only for its utility. The toilet rolls analogy mirrors the dismal and dishonorable treatment of the masses to peanuts during political campaigns and elections only to be abandoned thereafter but needed again during the next election season. *Usong-afere* and toilet roll suffer similar fate by their users. Similarly, this is the manner most Nigerian politicians treat the masses.

Accordingly, an *erotic* sort of relationship has been established between the political elites and the masses. In other words, the relationship between Nigerian politicians and the common people is largely characteristically profoundly transactional. Its dynamic is defined by deep mistrust, because while the politicians represent and serve their interests, they coax and woo the masses to vote for them. They also indulge in other unwholesome practices to cling onto political power. This relationship is transactional, exemplifying what may be described as master - slave rather than a representation that it ought to be. It is common knowledge that Nigerian politicians work for themselves, families and cronies. This hypothetical, transactional manipulation is the gravest expression of the unholy attitudes of most politicians towards the Nigerian masses. As the attitude of most politicians cannot be universalized, there rises the need for a change

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of attitude to that which can engender a categorical imperative.

Our politicians must be intentionally ‘righteous’ in doing what is right and upholding the dignity and welfare of the people in their policies formulation and actions. This is because the very poor people that are undermined are the source of their political power and wealth. The poor masses are the political wealth of the nation. As Okon notes, the human person is wealth of inestimable value himself, it is the human person that is wealth in himself and source and means of wealth acquisition. Therefore, subjecting them to hypothetical and transactional treatment that undermines both their dignity and welfare is unacceptable. In his analysis, Okon equiperates the human person with wealth as follows: “the conceptualization and usage of ‘imo’ transcends wealth merely considered as material wherewithal. ‘Imo’ in annang language, literature and philosophy entails the valuables in entirety the highest of which is the human person (akuk ade akuk, awo ade inyene = money is money, only the human person is wealth)” (2014, p. 81). No wealth is greater than the human person. In the context under interrogation, it is the masses who are human that are the source of the ‘ill-gotten’ wealth of the politicians. Justice (one of the principles of democracy) demands that the people be given their due and not be given *usong-afreere* treatment and attitude. Having and showing concern for the masses, values and attitudes capable of translating the potential of

the masses to concrete realities are as well recognized as wealth in Annang cultural milieu. Indeed, whatever possesses the quality that can uplift the masses in the worth of his life – whether physical or metaphysical, material or immaterial are reckoned as wealth (Okon, 2014, p. 81). There must be consistency, therefore, between the electoral promises, especially while canvassing for votes and delivering democratic dividends when finally voted into office. It is for this reason that Okon hits the nail on the head as he clearly advances that “imo ade awo” as articulated, comes as a clarion call for the revaluation of modern behavioral patterns which, hitherto, pose danger or threats to human progress the world over. Hence, it is primarily an ethical advocacy in the interest of man as man” (Okon, 2014, p. 83). It must be emphasized that while politicians amass wealth for themselves, they must also think about the masses in consistency with their electoral promises. Values of consistency and honesty make people and institutions honorable. How can inconsistent and dishonest politicians be addressed as honorable and excellencies? It is contradictory to address an inconsistent and dishonest person as ‘honorable’ and ‘excellency’. Our politicians must be consistent to merit their title of “honorable” and “excellency”.

There are several implications and consequences of the negative attitude of politicians for healthy democratic experience. Studies abound on this subject matter, but a particular study reveals that there is a great correlation between

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fulfilment of electoral promises to the citizenry and their participation in electoral processes. One of the implications is political alienation which according to him “connotes the relative continued feeling of rejection or estrangement from the prevailing political environment by the individual citizen. The politically alienated individuals desire to vote, but their feeling of insignificance to the system restricts them” (Igiebor, 2022, p. 23). The estrangement is due to the attitude of some political elites, and this grossly affects credible elections so long as it influences disfranchisement of some electorates. This, therefore, demands a change of attitude for better and credible electoral experiences.

Simili modo, (Finifter, 1970, Pp.389-410) identified five different ways in which political alienation expresses itself firstly, as political powerlessness, where an individual feels that he cannot influence political action and electoral results, thus, feeling himself estranged. Secondly, meaninglessness, where one feels that political and governmental actions and activities are not clear to him. Thirdly, political normlessness where one feels a deviation of government form regulation and acceptable ways of practice. This invariably must impact negatively on governmental outcomes. Fourthly, political isolation which outrightly rejects widely shared behavior by others in the polity. Lastly, political disappointment manifests in the lack of interest in government activities because of the feeling that the government has indulged in some criminal activities without proper

sanctions. These variants of political alienation are detrimental to electoral practices and democracy in general and so raise the need for political elites to change their attitude. This means that wide political participation flourishes in an enabling political atmosphere safe enough to attract wide participation and confidence in the system. This new vision that engenders wide range inclusivity will also enhance political participation and better electoral results.

In sum, the attitudes of the majority of Nigerian politicians towards the masses is simply appalling. They show so much hypothetical use of the people instead of doing what is good for goodness’ sake. Most of what they do is hypocritical and their relationship with the people transactional. But to this attitude, Emmanuel Levinas will simply say “responsibility for the other has not been a return to oneself” (1974, p. 114). It must be for goodness’ sake, after all care for the other is primordial and comes after care for oneself as Levinas advocates, “relationship with the non-ego, precedes any relationship of the ego with itself. The relationship with the other precedes the auto affection of certainty which one always tries to reduce communication” (1974, p. 119). As it concerns politicians that officially pledged to serve the people, Levinas’ advocacy is a serious indictment of their failure. Their calculated withdrawal and avoidance of communication with the masses is a strategy to keep themselves estranged from the people. This attitude is inconsistent with their

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promises, antithetical to the constitution and their campaign promises, illogical, and contradicts logical principles, hence, dishonorable (contradicts and in contrast to their empty political titles e.g. honorable, his Excellency etc.). However, democracy being the government of the people prioritizes the people's welfare via its principles and structures, but the direct contrary is the case in Nigeria as is obvious in the dismal welfare/wellbeing of the people.

4) Everydayness of the Nigerian people

Everydayness here refers to life realities that confront the Nigerian people. The everydayness of Nigerian masses is characterized by sorry tales of misery, a strong indicator of absence of welfare for the citizenry. Welfare or well-being may be understood as the "level of prosperity or standard of living of individuals or groups of people. Welfare is more often used when referring to groups of people, implying that individual well-being must be added up in some way" (Dasgupta and Edenhofer, 2018, p. 142). Welfare has multiple indicators and it assesses the realities of daily life such as poverty and inequality among the citizenry, the environment and other basic amenities including access to health care and educational facilities. Welfare is a concept of norm because it prescribes what is important to a society, for instance, it indicates indices of happy people as well as capabilities to function. Furthermore, it is also assessed via the economy of society (Dasgupta and Edenhofer, 2018, p. 142). In this sense, economic growth of

a country could be used to determine the welfare of people, but it does not always correlate with the people's actual welfare. It, therefore, implies here that claims of economic growth must impact visibly on the lives of the citizenry before the claims could rightly be made. Unfortunately, the everydayness of Nigerian citizenry even in this century is still characterized by want for biological needs such as food, medicare, social welfare and education. Food in Abraham Maslow's hierarchy of needs belongs to biological needs which are the lowest human needs. It is these basic human needs that the citizens clamor for everyday of their lives. Challenges in fulfilling the lowest ebbs of human needs are indications that higher human needs are far from being fulfilled. This challenging scenario questions the possibility of welfare where the basic human needs are yet to be provided for. In what follows are further highlights and analysis of the everydayness of the citizenry.

Two major crises in contemporary Nigeria are economic hardship and insecurity. Other strands of Nigeria's everydayness are either variants or constituents of these two. Social and economic crises may be caused by an exponential youth population together with structural and systematic weaknesses manifested by serial corruption and dearth of vision by leaders and absence of visionary leadership. Another cause is lack of necessary skills for gainful employment by available employers. This may account only for a little

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percentage of the population. The above factors have impacted negatively on the socio-economic status quo of many Nigerians especially the youths and consequently, their parents and guardians continue to be in penury so long as they continue providing for the upkeep of their wards. This problem also engenders disparity in income and welfare of the citizenry.

Despite Nigeria's wealth in natural resources, the impact on the socio-economic life of its citizenry leaves one in deep and unthinkable wonder. Unemployment in Nigeria especially among the youth and women has steadily increased in recent decades, with current figures reaching alarming levels. Records from the National Bureau of Statistics of (NBS, 2020), reveals that Nigeria's unemployment rate stood at 27.1% in 2020, and unemployment among the youth exceeds 40%. Unemployment is a serious factor to the socio-economic life of Nigeria which sustains negative impacts on their everydayness. Youth unemployment is so high, hence, some of them indulge in crime either as a means of livelihood or just occupying their empty lives. Essentially, unemployment may be understood as a situation whereby those that are ready and qualified and available for work do not have work available for them. It is a statement of fact that there is a high rate of unemployment in Nigeria. In his analysis on unemployment in Nigeria, Gado affirms its reality and connects it to one the causes of disparity in income among the citizenry: "High unemployment rates often lead to greater income disparities, as the

unemployed are unable to earn wages, while those who remain employed may face reduced earnings due to downward pressure on wages" (2025, p. 2). Apart from this, those that are employed are also faced with the risks of being laid off and low wages as employers may be unwilling to pay higher salaries since the employed can always be replaced. Several Nigerians over the years have been made to live this reality everyday of their lives. Furthermore, there exist different types of unemployment such as structural, cyclical, and frictional unemployment. Whereas structural unemployment arises from a mismatch between the skills and the requirements of the labor market, for lack of the needed education and vocational training, cyclical unemployment results from economic downturns, especially constant and sudden changes in the price of crude oil on which Nigeria's economy highly depends. Frictional unemployment is the short-term loss of job that occurs as individuals switch between jobs or people that get employment for the first time (Gado, 2025, p.2). Unemployment among Nigerian youths may take one or all of these types and it is a matter of concern though the government has not done enough to ameliorate the hardship and ignominy caused by it.

The above being the types of unemployment and the reasons for which the masses are without means of living, calls on the government to equip the citizenry as well as create job opportunities. The above situation interrogates the efficiency

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with which the nation's wealth is managed. However, the wealth of the nation, properly used and judiciously managed, is sufficient to create enough employment opportunities for all as well as equip the youth with requisite skills for jobs. The diversion of the nation's wealth into private pockets of politicians for their selfish motives and self-aggrandization at the expense and detriment of the masses is one of the major causes of the current hardship among the teeming population. The constant and intentional misappropriation of the national wealth is convertible to preying on them. This is cannibalism. "Cannibalism in democracy refers to the experience where leaders appropriate, apportion and arrogate to themselves the resources that should have served the common good. It includes indifference to insecurity, unaccountability, money laundering, embezzlement of public funds, awarding contracts to unjustifiable sums only to abandon them, subverting the will of the people, all manners of electoral fraud, miscarriages of justice in the courts of law. These and similar malpractices constitute democratic cannibalism" (Esikot and Adahada, 2024, p.76). Lack of job opportunities for the people is the basis of economic hardship, and it is strongly connected to insecurity that has ravaged the country for years now.

National insecurity, therefore, refers to the vulnerability of a country to internal threats that endanger its safety, stability, and sovereignty. In Nigeria, insecurity originated from local terror

groups such as Boko Haram, bandits, terrorist herders, kidnappers and other sources but allegedly sponsored by persons and international terrorist groups. Furthermore, Nigeria's experience of terrorism features military attacks, civilian attacks of diverse dimensions, economic crises, cyber threats, and a general atmosphere of fear and panic. And in the condition of insecurity, economic hardship is aggravated. Esikot and Adahada, (2024, p.77) note: "Currently, insecurity is still hounding the masses and certain parts of the country are just not safe as people are killed even in their houses, on the roads, places of worship and in places where they make their livelihood like the farms and so on. Insecurity is unarguably the greatest threat to Nigeria's nascent democracy". In the southern part of Nigeria, there is the menace of kidnapping for ransom and armed robbery. Several lives have been lost in the process. In the northern part of the country, there is the problem of a mindless sect, Boko Haram that has wasted several lives and destroyed property worth billions of Naira. In addition to Boko Haram terrorism in the North, there are bandits and terrorist herders. All these are essentially, terrorist groups so long as they terrorize armless and defenseless citizens. The everydayness of ordinary Nigerians is a complex of ugly situations that demands the political will of the leaders to resolve for a better experience. For instance, some high-ranking politicians opine that insecurity is politically motivated. "Godswill Akpabio [the president of Nigerian 10th senate],

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once said that the recent upsurge in insecurity across parts of the country was politically motivated, ahead of the 2027 general elections. He said the attempts were to discredit President Bola Tinubu, adding that two weeks after the general elections, the attacks and bombing would fizzle out” (Vanguard News online). However, this is a country where names of individuals and groups have been published as the sponsors of terrorism. The mention of political will has multiple implications but it begins with the decision to make a change. To begin with, the country’s constitution needs to be reviewed sincerely to reflect the will and needs of the citizenry as well as giving leverage for solving imminent problems. Going forward, the following must be reviewed: 1) the academic curriculum at all levels of education must be more practical than the current one that is more of theories. 2) Vocational education must be taught at the secondary school level. 3) Polytechnics should prioritize technical education where much attention is paid to practical knowledge instead of theories and unnecessary competition with university degrees for recognition. In this way students would be taught that education serves the purpose of creating jobs where graduates become job creators rather than job hunters. There is a need for total overhaul and reorientation and attitudinal change among politicians for a better country. If this is left undone, the fate of the people will remain that of *usong afere* in a woman’s pot of soup.

Economic hardship in the current dispensation is experienced in the severe inflation that has consumed the Nigerian market. Umaru and Zubairu (2012) uphold that inflation is a constant and continual increase in the general prices of goods and services at a certain location over an extended period. It is their opinion that inflation is associated with too much money pursuing fewer goods and services. According to Nigeria bureau of statistic,

Nigeria’s annual inflation rate eased slightly to 15.06% in February 2026 from 15.10% in the previous month, marking the lowest level since November 2020 and the 11th consecutive month of declining inflation. However, the pace of disinflation has slowed in the past two months, following a small interest rate cut by the Central Bank of Nigeria, which signaled expectations that inflation will continue to slow-down. Despite the overall slowdown, food inflation, traditionally the main driver of headline prices in the country, rose to 12.12% in February from 8.89% in January. The National Bureau of Statistics recently introduced a revised methodology for calculating inflation, shifting to a 12-month reference period instead of relying on a single-month comparison. (National Bureau of Statistics, Nigeria).

Unfortunately, the often claim of growth in the GDP and decline in the rate of inflation do not reflect market reality. For the common man, prices of commodities in the market change multiple times in a day, thus inflicting excruciating economic hardship on them.

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The reality of inflation in Nigeria is greatly driven by the kind of economy it operates. The economy of Nigeria is said to be driven by petrol. This simply means that petrol is the primary source of power both for households, small and large-scale businesses and services. Food which agriculture produces is highly linked to and sensitive to inflation for several reasons. For instance, rise in cost of fertilizers, fuel, cost of operating machinery and cost of labor and transportation invariably affect the cost of food for the final consumers (Magaji, Musa, Ikechukwu & Ismail 2025). After the removal of fuel subsidies at the beginning of Tinubu's administration, prices of goods and services surged. It also eroded purchasing power, raising the cost of production of goods and services and devaluing the naira. Inflation and hardship have become the daily experience of most Nigerians, and harder for the masses. The impact of inflation on the everydayness of Nigerian masses is obvious. A study reveals the strong connection between food prices and food insecurity, particularly as it impacts on the poor masses, the low-income earners and their households. Thus, inflation raises food prices, thus making food and other essential commodities and services less affordable, and leading to food insecurity (Katuka, Magaji and Musa p. 5). However, the inability or better still, the unwillingness of the government to sincerely empathize with the daily life condition of the masses who are irreplaceable in their success during elections invariably means to jettison them. This

sidelining of the people is analogous to the fate of *usong-afere* in a woman's pot.

5. Fate of Usong-afere versus Nigerian Masses juxtaposed: responsibility, norm, or anomaly?

As a recap, the fate of *usong-afere* in a woman's pot is that it will be thrown out after it has fulfilled its role of making the soup delicious. This jettisoning after fulfilling its function is hypothetical use. *Simili modo*, Nigerian masses are abandoned after casting their votes for their popular political candidates, and on assuming office, the candidate (now a political officer) abandons the people by not fulfilling their political campaign promises. The people were just used to attaining their political success. It is at this juncture that the moral thoughts of Immanuel Kant come to bear. The politicians in question appropriate the electorates for their use at the time. Having been used to reach an end, they were used hypothetically. But human beings must not be used hypothetically for any action whatsoever. According to Kant, "If the action would be good only as a means to something else, the imperative is hypothetical; but if the action is thought of as good in itself and hence as necessary in a will that conforms to reason, which it has as its principle, the imperative is categorical" (Kant, 2008 p. 19). It is crystal clear that the behavior and action of most politicians in Nigeria towards the masses show that they only appropriate the masses as means to their success in politics. The recurring but simple question is: can such an approach

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engender universal law? Answering affirmatively implies agreeing with the maltreatment of the masses by the political officers. It means endorsing using the masses as means to achieve their political ambitions without a corresponding dispensing of the gains of democracy. This is evil. This attitude is irresponsibility in the ordinary sense of the word. In the ethics of Emmanuel Levinas, it is an ethical violation because the politicians have deviated from answerability incumbent on them. For Levinas, responsibility is the primary structure of subjectivity that is fundamental for his existence as a moral persona (Levinas 1985, p. 95). So construed, responsibility in view refers to our answerability for what we did not do, for what does not concern us, for what we are not obliged to. However, the politicians are obligated to answer for the promises they made, the scenarios they created, for the actions they initiated or have failed to initiate. On the contrary, Levinas' notion of responsibility calls to question what we did not do, for what does not concern us. It imposes a duty on us, namely, coming to the rescue, to help the other person because his condition needs help and the person that sees him is the only person available to render the help. This is the mainstream of his notion of ethical responsibility. In his own words, "I understand responsibility as responsibility for the other, thus as responsibility for what is not my deed, or for what does not even matter to me" (Levinas, 1985, p. 95). This notion of responsibility where

one obliges answerability for another person for what he did not cause or for what does not even matter to him departs from Levinas' ethical Didache which is also a deconstruction of Martin Heidegger's notion of human thrownness. In his notion of thrownness, Heidegger postulated that man, being born into the world, is left to his fate and cannot be helped by another person but must help himself in any situation that he finds himself in. The thrownness [Geworfenheit] of man in the world, Heidegger calls it the facticity of its being. This means that man is abandoned in the world to cater for himself, to bear the burden of his existence (Heidegger 2010, p. 131). This notion leaves man hopeless in contradistinction to Levinas' ethics of responsibility. Levinas' notion of responsibility is a response and a deconstruction of such a bleak fate of man's existence. It offers both ethical and moral responses as well as interrogates the abnormal approach taken by some of Nigeria's politicians.

To restore man from the Heideggerian despair and hopelessness to optimism, Levinas' philosophy, the ethics of responsibility is indispensable. It is precisely for this reason that Levinas claims that his ethics is first philosophy because it interrogates the concrete daily life situation of man who himself is the subject and object of philosophizing (Levinas 1989, pp 75-87). Furthermore, Levinas avers that in human life situations, an individual's relation with another is primordial to relationship with oneself. With this avowal, Levinas explains why

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in one's ethical existence, relationship with the other, since it is primordial, is prioritized over relation with the self. Specifically, he defends, "in expiation, the responsibility for the others, relationship with the non-ego precedes any relationship of the ego with itself" (Levinas, 1974, p. 119). Levinasian ethics does not imply self-abnegation as some critics think, but it entails a prioritization of otherness to the extent that it restores the lost hope and care of others. It entails alleviating others from the burden of their thrownness. Levinas' ethics of responsibility calls Nigerian politicians to question. It interrogates their lack of answerability to the electorates and points the trajectory to inclusive enjoyment of democratic dividends. A recap on the *raison d'être* for Levinas' ethical voyage perfectly aligns with his ethical postulations and interrogations. Man must be cared for: he that initiates the care, Levinas calls the subject. The subject is the benefactor so long as he answers and offers help for the good of the beneficiary. Levinas characterizes the benefactor in a superlative way such that he is always available, ready and willing to offer help to the beneficiary. On the flip side is the beneficiary which he calls the other (Levinas uses "Other" to distinguish all the human "Other" from non-human "other"). The other is directly opposite the subject as he is infinitely in need and depends on the care of the subject for his daily survival. The answerability of the subject to the other implies care, hospitality, solidarity and welfare the wealthy

people ought to provide for the indigent of the society. This concrete expression of care is a response to the suffering and the hardship staring on the Other's faces and begging for survival. Emmanuel Levinas explains his notion of responsibility in his major philosophical works and beyond (Levinas 1969, p. 119; Levinas 1985, pp. 95ff; Levinas, 1974, pp. 55-59). The nexus in the relationship between some Nigerian politicians and the mass described above as the fate of *usong-afere* is a situation which Levinas' notion of responsibility gravely condemns. In what follows, is a juxtaposition of Levinas' analysis of his responsibility notion meant as ethical principle and the discharge of official duty as Nigeria's constitution demands. The condemnation of the fate of *usong-afere* bothers firstly with the reason of constitutional nature and obligation of political officers to be responsible to the electorates. This is to say, a politician vies for a political office and is consequently voted into office. In the office, his duty assumes constitutional and moral dimensions. Constitutional, because he takes an oath of office using the Nigerian legal code to uphold the demands of the office. The 1999 constitution of Nigeria as amended spells out oaths of office for different political officers. It is interesting how the oath of office of governors and the president ends with the vow "and that I will devote myself to the service and well-being of the people of Nigeria" (Nigeria Constitution, 1999 section 7). From their behavior and actions, it does appear that the oath is a formality.

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Morally, political officers are bound both by moral law and the ethical principle of Levinas which are intentionally and clearly encapsulated in the Nigerian constitution. Since the oath is constitutional, politicians ought to be intentional about the welfare and well-being of the masses. Maltreatment, irresponsible behavior viz abandonment of the masses and jettisoning them like the proverbial *usong-afere* should never be heard of. The people must be cared for just like Levinas would say “despite oneself, starting with oneself, the pain of labor in the patience of aging, in the duty to give to the other the bread out of one’s own mouth and the coat from one’s shoulders” (Levinas 1974, p. 55). Politicians, if they are of service to the electorate, must prioritize the welfare of the electorates over their selfish interests. Furthermore, elsewhere, Levinas impersonating the subject (which in this context is the political officers) says “I am responsible for him...his responsibility is incumbent on me” (Levinas 1985, p. 96). Unfortunately, it is doubtful if any Nigerian politician can make such a claim in truth. Nevertheless, in these pages, Levinas explains the ethical authority and the duty Nigerian politicians possess to assume responsibility to the masses and most especially, the less privileged ones. In what is more stunning, Levinas identifies the masses as nakedness, face and destituteness. He claims that to see and recognize the electorates for whose sake the political officers take oath of office to serve, is to recognize their hunger, suffering, and to feed

them and provide their basic needs (Levinas 1969, p.75). ‘Hunger and feeding’ must be understood metaphorically to signify providing good governance where dividends of democracy in terms of good economy, amenities and facilities are made available for the welfare and well-being of the people. The fate of Nigerians in a democratic government should be an experience of responsibility in Levinas’ notion. Further questions triggered by the metaphor of *usong-afere* analogous to the treatment of Nigerian people by some political officers is the question of norm. A norm could be analyzed from several perspectives. Philosophically, it may be perceived as an accepted rule or standard; principle or an approach that guides human behavior or beliefs; judgements or evaluation, that distinguishes ‘what ought to be’ from ‘what actually is’. From this preliminary analysis, norms regulate human thoughts, behavior and actions by prescribing and permitting them. They also forbid certain other actions as well as checking certain other actions, beliefs and feelings. A norm is a regulator of human behavior, mentality and actions. Of norms, Korsgaard writes that they make claims of us, they oblige and command us, and they recommend or guide us. It means that when we agree that an action is right, it commands us to do it and so we ought to do it. When we say something is good, we invariably recommend it as worthy of choice (1996, pp. 8-9). It could be understood from the following that moral norms are objective in the sense that those that bind

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themselves to their prescriptions are those that accept their guidance. It is not objective in the sense of absolute objectivity as a palpable feature or property found in the world. Furthermore, norms are self-legislated, accepted and imposed on their adherents. Norms are pragmatic in nature as they are potent and useful in resolving practical issues. Because of this functionality, they become binding forces of moral duties, arising from the inner nature of man rather than external.

According to Émile Durkheim, a French sociologist, a “norm is a social rule, functioning as a "social fact" that is external to the individual, coercive, and shapes behavior to maintain social order and collective consciousness” (Durkheim 1895, p. 13). This definition aligns with that offered by Korsgaard. The underlying idea is that individuals bound by a given norm order their actions in line with it. A question arising from this is if a bad and wrong approach to doing things can assume the *status quo* of a norm? From the analysis above, this can be answered affirmatively. A behavior engendering a norm does not automatically mean that the norm is accepted or right. A norm can be accepted by certain adherents and nevertheless remains wrong and objectionable by other people outside the circle of those that accept it. A social norm is a shared, often unspoken rule or expectation about how people ought to behave within a group, community, or culture, and these standards can be harmful, unethical, or destructive, it nevertheless can cease to be a

norm because its adherents are guided by it. The harm and destruction such behaviors visit on the community is the matter of concern of the remaining part of this section. In addition is the question of whether such behavior accruing from such norms could assume a universal law. The subject of deliberation has been the abnormal treatment of the electorates in Nigeria that has been normalized by political officers. Could this treatment be called normal or an anomaly or abnormalized norm? It seems “abnormal” in the sense that these politicians have deviated from the typical expectations. Furthermore, it is abnormal because it proceeds in a negative way that proves unhealthy or problematic to the electorates’ welfare and well-being. It does not bear out the dividends of democracy. Similarly, it also impacts negatively on the politicians as the electorates will develop apathy in future elections seasons. The cumulative impact of abnormal behavior of Nigerian politicians is antithetical and destructive to democracy.

However, democracy is generally considered and recognized as an ideal form of government with values and principles to foster it. United Nations Human Right succinctly declares that “democracy is a universally recognized ideal based on common values shared by people across the world, irrespective of cultural, political, social and economic differences” (UNHR). At the core of democratic values and principles are justice, equity, fairness and sincerity. Political officers are obliged to uphold

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these values in their relationship with the electorates not only at electioneering seasons but always. Absence of these values invariably implies poor return of democratic dividends for the electorate. Together with the United Nation declaration is the stipulation by the 1999 constitution of the Federal government of Nigeria where security of lives and welfare of citizenry is at the core of the primary responsibility of government. Security and welfare must be provided and guaranteed by the government who are political officers. Unfortunately, this expectation is much inadequately delivered, hence the feelings of the fate of *usong-afere* metaphor needing resolution. The United Nation Human Rights office has highlighted several aims of democracy which it claims are interdependent and mutually enforcing. For example, it claims that they “preserve and promote the dignity and fundamental rights of the individual; achieve social justice; foster the economic and social development of the community; strengthen the cohesion of society; enhance national tranquility; and create a climate that is favorable for international peace” (UNHR). Ideal as this aim may be, they can only be translated into reality in climes that have true democracy. In these countries, politicians know that they are for the service of the people and not to gratify their selfish motives. To achieve this goal, democratic principles and values are the compass of political actions. The value of transparency and accountability in public

administration makes it incumbent on politicians to mean what they say and say what they mean. However, most times they ignore this value and dismiss its entailments simply as “politics”, an attitude that is destructive to the integrity of democracy itself. The fate of *usong-afere* can never be a norm or political virtue in Nigeria. It is an anomaly. The ethical responsibility of Levinas deconstructs the *usong-afere* treatment which Nigerian politicians mete out on the electorates.

5) Conclusion.

In all civilized climes, democratic power belongs to the electorates. In Nigeria, the Nigerian electorates properly understood are the employers of the political officers because they have the power and vote them to office. The electorates are constant variables because they are always there to decide who to vote for in office. If these claims are true, between the electorates and the politicians, who deserves the *usong-afere* treatment? The electorates or the politicians? I think politicians may deserve it and should be removed if they fall short of the demand of their office. For as political officers voted for offices, they are tools of development, welfare and security for the electorates and where they fail to bear out the demands of their office and for which they solemnly swore an oath, they should be jettisoned. However, the reverse is the case in Nigeria’s democratic experiences. Most politicians serve themselves and their interests and those of their families

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and political allies and cronies, thus, leaving the masses to their fate.

The usong-afere treatment of the Nigerian masses is an anomaly in a true democratic setting. The reason is simply because it is a deviation from the norm, which is acting in consonance with the principles and values of democracy. However, as an anomaly it is a departure from the common rule of justice, fairness, equity, transparency expected from democratic leaders as constituted norm in democracy. Unjust treatment or injustice towards electorates is unexpected from democrats that donate themselves to services of the people for the people. It indicates irregularity, inconsistency, or abnormality which can be pinned down to the intentions of the politicians before aspiring to the office, processes through which the leaders emerged and the quality – personal character and integrity of the politicians. Since the electorates are truly the employers of the politicians, it is incumbent on them to jettison any politician that misfits the offices for which he vied.

Abandoning the electorates after elections, not fulfilling campaign promises are “mortal sins” of democracy. They are unpardonable sins. Unfortunately, this sin thrives in undemocratic climes where politics are viewed as full-time jobs and the quickest way of amassing wealth through embezzlement of public funds. To fit the mighty, the processes are mitigated and compromised and hence the outcome, abandonment of the electorates. This kind of

politics thrives in third-world countries. Fraudulent political elites often defend their mismanagement by labelling it as nascent democracy. This is self-stultifying.

The founders of the United Nations were said to have been silent on the use of the word “democracy” when they were drafting the United Nations Charter. Similarly, when in 1945 member states did not endorse democracy as system of government, yet they agreed that the system of the government must be people centered and so, in the charter, the following were concretely inserted: ““We the Peoples”, reflect the fundamental principle of democracy - that the will of the people is the source of legitimacy of sovereign states and, therefore, of the United Nations as a whole” (UN, Peace, Dignity and Equality on healthy Planet). This again reiterates the fact that power belongs to the people and that the people should not and can never be abandoned in true democratic governance else it becomes an oddity. Rather, protection of fundamental human rights, obedience to rule of law, fairness and justice, accountability and transparency will inform meaningful participation by the people leading to effective governance of which social cohesion and inclusivity will bear out sustainability called dividends of democracy. In this experience, no one will be excluded and no one will be abandoned. Democracy will resonate with its name: ‘government of the people for the people and by the people’.

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